

Derivatives of Imidazole

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The synthesis of some 3:6-disubstituted imidazo (2,1-b)-thiazoles, 2:7-disubstituted imidazo (2,1-b)-benzothiazoles, 2-substituted imidazo (1,2-a) pyrimidines and 2-substituted imidazo (2,1-b)-naphthothiazoles have been described. The antifungal and antihistaminic activities of some of these compounds are reported.

The chemotherapeutic importance of imidazole derivatives is well recognised¹⁻³. Some 5-substituted triazeno imidazole-4-carboxamides have been found to be potential anticancer agents⁴. The effectiveness of condensed heterocycles containing pyridine, pyrimidine, thiazole and imidazole rings as antibacterials, antiprotozoal agents⁵, anticonvulsants⁶, antidepressants⁷, antihelminthic agents⁸⁻¹¹, and as inhibitors of dihydrofolate¹² led us to synthesise some imidazothiazoles, imidazobenzothiazoles, imidazonaphthothiazoles and imidazopyrimidines. The compounds synthesised are classified into four types.

- (i) 3 : 6-Disubstituted imidazo (2, 1-b) thiazoles.
- (ii) 2 : 7-Disubstituted imidazo (2, 1-b)-benzothiazoles.
- (iii) 2-Substituted imidazo (2, 1.b)-naphthothiazoles.
- (iv) 2-Substituted imidazo (1, 2-a)-pyrimidines.

The imidazothiazoles, imidazobenzothiazoles, imidazonaphthothiazoles and imidazopyrimidines were prepared by condensation and simultaneous cyclisation of substituted w-bromo-acetophenones with 2-amino thiazoles, 2-amino benzothiazoles, 2-amino naphthothiazoles and 2-amino pyrimidines respectively. The intermediates 4-substituted-2-aminothiazoles were prepared by condensation of corresponding ketones with thiourea in presence of iodine¹³⁻¹⁶. 2-Amino-6-substituted benzothiazoles and 2-amino-naphthothiazoles were prepared by the method reported by Bhargava and coworkers⁷. In order to study whether addition of another heterocyclic ring might result into a different spectrum or order of pharmacological activity, monobromo methyl thienyl ketone was used in place

of substituted w-bromo acetophenones for the synthesis of imidazothiazoles.

By analogy with the quarterisation of 4-aryl-2-amino thiazoles by alkyl halide and synthesis of imidazo (2, 1-b)-thiazolidines¹⁸, it is assumed that the phenacyl or substituted phenacyl group enters at position 3 of the thiazole ring first and then cyclisation proceeds. That initial alkylation does occur at ring nitrogen in these heterocycles has been unequivocally established by several other workers¹⁹⁻²¹. The structure of the bicyclic compounds are consistent with the infrared spectra which showed no absorption around 3350-3450 cm^{-1} (absence of NH_2 group) and 1690-1710 cm^{-1} region (absence of $\text{C}=\text{O}$ group). The U. V. absorption spectra of the compounds and their protonated forms are similar to those reported by Hulbert and coworkers²²⁻²³ in case of pyrido (2, 3-d) pyrimidines.

Experimental :

I. R. spectra were determined on Perkin Elmer 337 grating infrared spectrophotometer in Nujol mull, U. V. spectra on Beckmann DU 2 spectrophotometer in ethanol. The C, H, N analysis of imidazopyrimidines were performed in I. I. T. Kanpur.

2-Amino-4(2'-thienyl)-thiazole was prepared from 2-acetylthiophene, thiourea and iodine (loc. cit.) (m.p. 185°, yield 70%. Found S, 34.78%, N, 14.85%, $\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{N}_2\text{S}_2$ requires S, 35.17%, N, 15.38%).

3 : 6-Diphenyl imidazo (2, 1-b) thiazole :

A mixture of phenacyl bromide (1.9 g, 1 mole), 4-phenyl-2-aminothiazole (3.5 g, 2 moles) in absolute alcohol (30-35 ml) was heated under reflux in a water bath maintained at 70° for about 6 hrs. After the

reaction was over the product was cooled when the crystals appeared. This was filtered and recrystallised from glacial acetic acid. m.p. 196°, yield 80% (Found S, 11.28%, N, 9.65%, C₁₇H₁₃N₃S requires S, 11.60%, N, 10.15%).

The melting point, yield and the analytical data of other imidazothiazoles are given in Table 1.

2-(p-chloro phenyl) imidazo (2, 1-b) benzothiazole : (Table 2).

A mixture of 2-amino benzothiazoles (0.8 g) and *p*-chlorophenacyl bromide (1.4 g) in absolute alcohol (40-45 ml) was refluxed in a water bath at 70° for 6 hrs. Excess of solvent was evaporated off and the mixture was cooled when the compound appeared. This was filtered and recrystallised from alcohol, repeatedly to a constant melting point.

2-(p-Ethoxy phenyl) imidazo (2, 1-b) naphtho (2, 1-d) thiazole : (Table 3).

A mixture of 2-amino (2, 1-d naphthothiazole (2.0 g), *p*-ethoxy phenacyl bromide (1.21 g) in

absolute alcohol was refluxed and the compound was isolated as mentioned in the case of 3, 6-Diphenyl imidazo (2, 1-b) thiazole.

2-(p-Methoxy phenyl) imidazo (1, 2-a) pyrimidine hydrobromide :

2-Aminopyrimidine (1.1 g) and *p*-methoxy phenacyl bromide (2.2 g) were refluxed in absolute alcohol (30-35 ml) at 70° in a water bath for 4 hrs., when a precipitate was gradually separated. The precipitate was filtered off, washed repeatedly in alcohol and dried in vacuum ; m.p. 252°, yield, 85%, (Found N, 13.92%, Br, 26.61% ; C₁₈H₁₈N₂BrO requires N, 13.72%, Br, 26.15%).

2-(*p*-methoxy phenyl) imidazo (1, 2-a) pyrimidine was obtained from the above hydrobromide on treatment with NH₄OH. The m.p., yield and analytical data of all the substituted imidazo pyrimidines are recorded in Table 4.

TABLE 1

Sl. No.	Nature of R	Nature of R'	M.P. °C	Yield %	% Sulphur		% Nitrogen	
					Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
1	Phenyl	P-Br-Phenyl	128	75	8.85	9.01	7.26	7.89
2	Phenyl	P-Cl-Phenyl	192	70	10.00	10.30	9.52	9.01
3	Phenyl	P-Methoxy-Phenyl	127	70	10.10	10.47	8.65	9.15
4	Phenyl	P-Tolyl	173	75	11.52	11.04	9.03	9.65
5	P-Tolyl	P-Methoxy-Phenyl	141	80	10.45	10.00	8.55	8.75
6	P-Tolyl	P-Tolyl	141	75	11.01	10.52	8.84	9.21
7	P-Methoxy-Phenyl	P-Tolyl	220	65	9.46	10.00	8.35	8.75
8	P-Methoxy-Phenyl	P-Methoxy-Phenyl	202	75	9.17	9.52	8.01	8.33
9	P-Methoxy-Phenyl	P-Cl-Phenyl	195	70	8.85	9.40	8.72	8.22
10	P-Methoxy-Phenyl	P-Br-Phenyl	186	65	8.81	8.31	7.70	7.27
11	P-Cl-Phenyl	Phenyl	172	80	10.72	10.30	8.55	9.01
12	P-Cl-Phenyl	P-Br-Phenyl	174	80	8.75	8.21	7.78	7.19
13	P-Br-Phenyl	P-Br-Phenyl	99	75	7.75	7.37	6.01	6.45
14	P-Br-Phenyl	P-Nitro-Phenyl	194	75	7.58	8.00	10.18	10.50
15	P-Ethoxy-Phenyl	P-Methoxy-Phenyl	197	65	8.82	9.14	8.52	8.00
16	P-Ethoxy-Phenyl	P-Tolyl	238	70	9.01	9.58	8.06	8.38
17	2'-Thienyl	Phenyl	77	75	22.15	22.69	10.45	9.93
18	2'-Thienyl	P-Tolyl	60	60	21.11	21.62	8.95	9.46
19	2'-Thienyl	P-Methoxy-Phenyl	110	65	20.01	20.51	8.36	8.97
20	2'-Thienyl	P-Ethoxy-Phenyl	105	65	19.11	19.63	8.12	8.59
21	2'-Thienyl	P-Cl-Phenyl	72	70	20.86	20.21	8.64	8.85
22	2'-Thienyl	P-Br-Phenyl	75	65	17.22	17.73	7.20	7.76
23	2'-Thienyl	β-Naphthyl	58	55	19.74	19.27	8.95	8.43
24	2'-Thienyl	4'-Biphenyl	55	60	17.35	17.87	7.26	7.82
25	2'-Thienyl	2'-Thienyl	53	65	33.03	33.33	9.18	9.72
26	Phenyl	2'-Thienyl	117	65	22.11	22.69	9.45	9.93
27	P-Cl-Phenyl	2'-Thienyl	177	65	19.85	20.21	8.36	8.85
28	P-Br-Phenyl	2'-Thienyl	172	60	17.34	17.73	7.19	7.76

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TABLE 2

Sl. No.	Nature of R	Nature of R'	M.P. °C	Yield %	% Sulphur		% Nitrogen	
					Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
29	H	Cl	218	75	10.84	11.25	9.50	9.84
30	H	C ₆ H ₅	160	75	9.30	9.81	8.22	8.59
31	CH ₃	Cl	203	70	10.25	10.72	9.01	9.38
32	CH ₃	OCH ₃	219	70	10.65	10.88	9.14	9.52
33	CH ₃	OC ₂ H ₅	75	65	10.72	10.39	8.48	9.08
34	Cl	H	182	75	10.70	11.25	9.51	9.84
35	Cl	OC ₂ H ₅	215	75	9.38	9.74	8.11	8.52
36	Cl	CH ₃	190	70	10.98	10.72	8.94	9.38
37	Cl	Cl	221	75	10.42	10.03	8.39	8.78
38	Cl	Br	138	70	8.61	8.80	7.43	7.70
39	Cl	C ₆ H ₅	197	70	8.49	8.88	7.52	7.76
40	Cl	OCH ₃	237	65	9.72	10.17	8.66	8.90

TABLE 3

Sl. No.	Nature of R	Nature of R'	M.P. °C	Yield %	% Sulphur		% Nitrogen	
					Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
41	(1, 2-d) Naphtho	OC ₂ H ₅	226	70	9.74	9.30	7.96	8.14
42	(1, 2-d) Naphtho	OCH ₃	206	70	9.25	9.70	8.13	8.48
43	(1, 2-d) Naphtho	Cl	230	75	9.17	9.57	8.02	8.38
44	(2, 1-d) Naphtho	Cl	184	75	9.22	9.57	7.96	8.38
45	(2, 1-d) Naphtho	CH ₃	116	75	10.28	10.17	8.51	8.90
46	(2, 1-d) Naphtho	OC ₂ H ₅	140	70	9.05	9.30	7.78	8.14

TABLE 4

Sl. No.	Nature of R	M.P. °C	Yield %	% Carbon		% Hydrogen		% Nitrogen	
				Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
47	H	227	70	73.85	73.84	4.11	4.61	21.08	21.54
48	C ₆ H ₅	240	70	79.25	79.71	4.98	4.79	15.70	15.50
49	CH ₃	242	65	74.10	74.64	5.46	5.26	20.60	20.09
50	OCH ₃	126	70	68.88	69.33	5.18	4.89	18.20	18.66
51	OC ₂ H ₅	203	75	69.90	70.30	5.85	5.44	17.01	17.57
52	Br	226	70	52.05	52.55	3.38	2.92	15.80	15.32
53	Cl	7250	70	63.20	62.75	3.65	3.48	18.00	18.30

Fungicidal activity :

Twentyfive compounds from different series were assayed *in vitro* against *Drehslera nodulosa*. The percentage of inhibition was calculated by the following expression

$$\% \text{ inhibition} = \frac{(Ac - At)}{Ac} \times 100$$

where Ac=Area of the colony in control plate ;
At=Area of the colony in test plate.

All the compounds tested showed considerable activity at the concentration 500 ppm, the % inhibition range being 98.85%. Compound Nos. 12, 31, 37, 38, 44, 45 and 52 are the most active compounds which indicate that the presence of naphthyl nucleus and halogens enhance the fungicidal properties of a compound.

Antihistaminic activity :

Fifteen compounds from the series imidazothiazoles (Table 1), imidazobenzothiazoles (Table 2) and imidazopyrimidines (Table 4) were tested for their ability to block histamine on the terminal ileum of guinea pig. All experiments were performed by assessing the response to a standard dose of histamine and by estimating the degree and duration for which the response was modified by prior administration of the test compounds. At a concentration 200 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, there was complete blockade in the case of compound Nos. 8, 9, 10, 27, and 51. The return of histamine response after washing was also slow in the case of above compounds.

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